

Landscape diversity indication from remote sensing data using open source software

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ABSTRACT

The paper is focused on landscape diversity indication using remote sensing data and open RS/GIS software (BEAM Visat and QGIS), to make a contribution to solving the urgent problem of biodiversity loss. About hundred indexes for landscapes diversity assessment are developed and described in scientific literature, but they often give a different or even an opposite estimates of diversity. Thus there is a need for objective landscape diversity indication methods and tool, efficient for agricultural landscape structure monitoring. Of particular importance is also a way of grouping of structure elements (remote sensing data classification). This approach is based on remote sensing data processing using BEAM Visat software to determine the classes of agro landscape structure (land cover classes), and subsequent calculation of landscape metrics to select the most appropriate indexes for landscape diversity monitoring using QGIS and R software.

General Terms

Algorithms, Management, Measurement,

Keywords remote sensing, landscape diversity indexes, landscape metrics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Intensive agriculture is one of the essential factors of biodiversity loss at ecosystem, population and genetic levels due to simplified structure and fragmentation of landscapes, habitat isolation and reduction of areas with natural vegetation [1]. In Ukraine the rate of arable land in landscape structure is one of the highest in Europe and the world, reaching 72% of the country area [2].

One of the key goals of sustainable agricultural land management is achieving the environmentally-oriented agricultural landscape structure taking into account the landscape and watershed perspective, habitat connectivity, core areas distribution, and ecosystem carrying capacity, allowing farmers to produce more from a smaller area, and leave more land under natural vegetation. Thus the landscape structure assessment tool is required. The tool must be simple and quantitatively objective for analysis of different models of agroecosystem spatial organization and selection of the most appropriate for biodiversity conservation agrolandscape structure.

More than hundred landscape metrics (indexes of landscape structure) are described in scientific literature [3, 4]. But they often give a different or even an opposite estimates of diversity. As an example, the two most commonly used indicators of

diversity can be considered: Shenon entropy and dispersion. As a common assumption, the higher is the index value, the more diverse is the structure. However, the same structure can be interpreted as varied and as simple, depending on the measurement method. Landscape structure, which all components have the same area size, is interpreted as diverse by the Shenon entropy index (where it reaches a maximum), and the same time as homogeneous by the dispersion index (where it reaches zero). Thus, there is a need for substantiation of landscape diversity indexes, objective and effective for agricultural landscape structure monitoring and biodiversity conservation.

The purpose of the study was to develop a specific tool, based on QGIS software, efficient for landscape diversity assessment. The main tasks of the study were the following:

- to identify the indicators of landscape and biological diversity of agroecosystems of forest-steppe zone;
- to calculate the landscape structure indexes (landscape metrics) for test sites;
- to substantiate the optimal landscape metrics to assess the diversity by the example of test sites with different arable land area rate, which was considered as a standard of comparison;
- to develop an algorithm for landscape diversity evaluation in order to create the assessment plugin based on QGIS software.

2. METHODS

One of the widely used indicators of agro-landscape stability is the proportion of land areas with high anthropogenic pressure (urban areas, agricultural fields, industrial zones, etc.) and land areas with natural vegetation, which have an ecosystems stabilization function (forests, grasslands, wetlands, etc.).

In accordance with applicable Ukrainian standards, the percentage of arable land at the level of 60-80% is considered as unfavorable, corresponding to a catastrophic state of the landscape; at the level of 25-60% – as relatively favorable, and less than 25% – as favorable [2]. The optimal forest cover area rate for the forest-steppe zone is 17-23% of the total area [2].

From the biological diversity conservation perspective not only the optimal rate of natural land areas should be recognized, but also the minimal required area of a particular patch (the homogenous element of landscape structure) with natural vegetation to function as a habitat core area. The area size should ensure the efficient reproduction of the population and guaranteed

their existence and resistance for indefinitely long time. According to the European landscape ecologists for many types of vegetation such area is 200 m². However, the stability of population structure of such habitat size is quite small and there is a high risk of their degradation, whereas core areas, embedded in the structure of agricultural landscapes, have to optimize the nearby territories with high anthropogenic pressure, in particular, fields under intensive agriculture. Areas with natural vegetation of 0.5-1 ha provides biological protection within a radius of 2 km. Smaller core areas do not have such optimizing function [2].

The patch form is also important in the contest of landscape structure assessment, as narrow and elongated patches are subjected to edge effect, when part of the patch lose their natural properties and get the signs of transition zones, which ultimately reduces the total area of certain class. Thus, the more similar is a shape of a patch with natural vegetation to a circle, the more optimal is the territory in the terms of biodiversity conservation.

In the best-organized territory, all core areas should be connected by biological corridors. The optimality of the network is measured by the indexes of connectivity, resilience and distribution within the study area.

Therefore, to assess landscape diversity the following indicators were selected:

- the rate of land areas with anthropogenic pressure to the land areas with natural vegetation;
- the core area occurrence for each patch class of natural vegetation (patches with area size of 0.5 hectares or more and with shape close to a circle);
- the biological corridors occurrence connecting core areas (connectivity, aggregation and fractal dimension of patch classes at landscape level).

3. RESULTS

Three test sites with different ratio of arable lands were chosen for working out the methodology of landscape diversity indication and landscape metrics substantiation. Arable land ratio was selected as an indicator of landscape diversity, representing not only the level of dominance of one landscape class, but also the simplicity of landscape structure, as agricultural field mostly have squared shapes. The test sites were used as standards for comparison of a set of calculated landscape metrics to choose the most objective and representative indicators for biodiversity conservation.

Based on satellite images of test sites (RepidEye, Landsat and Spot satellite images) the classes of agrolandscape structure were determined and land-cover maps was developed (Figure 1). Image processing and classification was conducted using BEAM Visat software [5].

Test area #1 consists of 7 classes (urban, roads, arable land, forest, meadow, marsh, water objects) with the ratio of arable lands of 12%. Test area #2 has 8 classes (urban, road, arable land, forest, meadow, shrub, thin vegetation, water) with 59% of arable lands rate. The last test area #3 includes only 6 classes (urban, roads, arable land, forest, meadow, water objects) with arable land ratio of 65%. The third test area is not differ significantly from the second test site in term of arable land ratio, but has less landscape structure classes.

Figure 1. Land-cover maps of test sites

To evaluate the ratio of areas with anthropogenic pressure to areas with natural vegetation, and the percentage of particular class area

in the landscape (in particular, the ratio of arable lands and ratio of forest areas) a QGIS plugin was developed allowing to select the particular feature set (patch class) in dialog window and calculate the ratios.

Another QGIS plugin was developed to identify the core areas in the structure of landscapes, as python script running the following algorithm:

- create the polygon (patch feature class) centroid;
- create a circle with 0.5 ha area around centroid;
- select by location the polygons (patch feature class) fully containing created centroid circles feature class;
- save selected polygons as a new feature class, considered to be core areas.

To evaluate the test sites in terms of connectivity and aggregation the calculation of landscape metrics using Fragstat and R software was conducted. The results are demonstrated at Table 1.

Table 1. Landscape metrics of test sites.

Landscape Metrics Name	Test site 1	Test site 2	Test site 3
Radius of Gyration	591.4861	498.6768	454.4331
Fractal Index Distribution	1.1550	1.1257	1.0922
Contiguity Index Distribution	0.9145	0.9987	0.9990
Core Area Index	79.3903	86.4340	86.5687
Proximity Index Distribution	88.0593	211.6897	1971.8720
Similarity Index Distribution	1680536	972730	592911
Euclidean Nearest Neighbor Distance Distribution	205.2873	105.6699	27.5581
Interspersion & Juxtaposition Index	57.6052	66.7821	69.3283
Landscape Division Index	0.9426	0.9548	0.9573
Splitting Index	17.4160	22.0999	23.3991
Shannon's Diversity Index	1.2646	1.1705	1.0219
Simpson's Diversity Index	0.6724	0.5872	0.5282
Modified Simpson's Diversity Index	1.1161	0.8848	0.7512
Simpson's Evenness Index	0.7845	0.6711	0.6338
Modified Simpson's Evenness Index	0.5735	0.4255	0.4193

Using test sites as standards for comparison and taking as the most diverse the test site #1 and the least diverse the test site #3, the following landscape metrics were demonstrated to be the most effective: Fractal Index Distribution, Similarity Index Distribution, Shannon's Diversity Index, Simpson's Diversity Index, Modified Simpson's Diversity Index, Simpson's Evenness Index. Standard Fragstat 4.2 algorithms were used for metrics calculating [6], where:

- Fractal Index Distribution equals 2 times the logarithm of patch class perimeter divided by the logarithm of patch class area;
- Similarity Index Distribution equals the sum, over all neighboring patches class with edges within a specified distance of the focal patch class, of neighboring patch class area times a similarity coefficient between the focal patch type and the class of the neighboring patch, divided by the nearest edge-to-edge distance squared between the focal patch and the neighboring patch.
- Shannon's Diversity Index equals minus the sum, across all patch types, of the proportional abundance of each patch type multiplied by that proportion.
- Simpson's Diversity Index equals 1 minus the sum, across all patch types, of the proportional abundance of each patch type squared.
- Modified Simpson's Diversity Index equals minus the logarithm of the sum, across all patch types, of the proportional abundance of each patch type squared.
- Simpson's Evenness Index equals minus the sum, across all patch types, of the proportional abundance of each patch type multiplied by that proportion, divided by the logarithm of the number of patch types.

4. CONCLUSION

An excessive fragmentation of natural vegetation into isolated areas, the dominance of mono-culture in agriculture, the high proportion of arable land, and plowing of grasslands and steppe areas to the boundary of the forests or rivers cause the reduction of environmental sustainability of agroecosystems.

The landscape is subjected to the common system rule of required diversity and the general rule of a causal relationship, whereby the existence and function of any system are only possible if the system includes heterogeneous but interacting and complementary elements. Changes of any ecosystem component lead to changes of other elements and ecosystem as a whole. Landscape resistance is the ability of the landscape to maintain its invariant structure and functions under external influences (natural and anthropogenic). For sustainable agriculture there is a need to assess and monitor the structure of agroecosystems. In particular, it is necessary to find out how the landscape system is designed and what the functional ties between its elements are, and how it performs and might perform their natural functions.

QGIS plugins for landscape metrics calculation could be a powerful and easy-to-use tool for spatial planning and agrolandscape structure monitoring and selection of ecological optimal land use model by quantifying the shape, area and connectivity of habitats in the landscape.

5. REFERENCES

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